

MATRIX FOR DEVELOPING NETWORK COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE AND NETWORK ETIQUETTE

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Abstract

The article examines the conditions and factors influencing the formation of network communication culture and digital etiquette among university instructors and students in the context of rapid digital transformation in education. The paper substantiates the need for purposeful development of digital skills among both teachers and learners, as the growing use of digital technologies, online formats, and virtual learning environments requires a new level of interaction culture and adherence to norms of digital conduct. The proposed matrix of developmental levels of network communication culture and digital etiquette presents an interconnected set of competencies that ensure a progressive transition from the reproductive to the productive and ultimately to the creative level of their formation. Each level is characterized by a specific range of knowledge, skills, and modes of activity required for professionally responsible and ethical participation in the digital educational environment.

Keywords: network communication culture, digital etiquette, digital literacy skills, online collaboration, reflexive thinking, critical thinking skills, virtual interaction, higher education environment, digital competencies, educational digitalization.

Introduction

The XXI-st century is characterized by large-scale and rapid transformations driven by the intensive development of digital technologies. Robotics, 3D printing technologies, artificial intelligence systems, virtual interaction environments, and modern bio- and neuro-technologies are consistently integrated into the educational space, directly influencing the transformation of the content, mechanisms, and forms of educational activities.

Information and communication technologies are becoming a system-forming component of the educational environment, leading to its reorganization and orientation toward forming a digital ecosystem in higher education institutions. The higher education system faces the task of adapting to the new conditions of digital transformation, which requires rethinking traditional approaches to teaching and interaction among participants in the educational process.

In the context of the dominance of digital technologies, educational practice must respond to modern challenges while adhering to the norms, principles, and regulations of teaching, learning, and professional communication in the online environment. University faculty, alongside using traditional offline teaching forms, must demonstrate a high level of proficiency with digital tools and implement online and blended learning formats. At the same time, there is a growing need for educators to observe norms of digital culture and digital etiquette, as well as to purposefully develop students' skills in network interaction. Faculty who possess these competencies and integrate them into their professional activities exhibit higher competitiveness due to their developed network communicative culture and adherence to digital etiquette.

Contexte

In modern conditions, teachers and students need to possess digital skills. Therefore, it is essential to form digital culture and digital etiquette among both students and teachers in online spaces. It is important to teach adherence to digital etiquette norms, development of

skills for effective use of new digital technologies and educational resources, and formation of a culture of reflexive consumption of digital content and correct behavior in virtual environments.

The faculty of Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University has been conducting research from 2023 to 2025 on the topic "Customization of the system for forming network communicative culture and digital etiquette of faculty and students in the university's 'online community'" (headed by U.M. Abdigaparova).

As part of the research, A.D. Tanatova and Sh.Zh. Kolumbaeva also presented a matrix demonstrating the key skills of faculty necessary to achieve a high level of network communicative culture and digital etiquette. This matrix shows the interrelation of the development levels of network communicative culture (hereinafter - NCC) and digital etiquette (hereinafter - DE) based on the presence of specific skills.

The matrix for forming network communicative culture (hereinafter - NCC) and digital etiquette (hereinafter - DE) represents a systemic model that includes an interconnected set of skills ensuring the progressive development of these competencies among faculty. These skills serve as the basis for constructing a modern, technologically equipped educational space that contributes not only to achieving academic outcomes but also to the formation of ethically oriented and responsible participants in digital interaction.

Methodologie

The transition from the reproductive to the creative level of NCC and DE development implies a conscious understanding by the faculty of the importance of these competencies, necessary for effective pedagogical interaction in the context of digitalization.

The matrix identifies three levels of NCC and DE development:

- the reproductive level is based on the integration of subject-specific, pedagogical, and technological knowledge.

- the productive level involves mastery of critical thinking skills, reflection, and communicative activities, including digital communication.

- the creative level is characterized by developed digital literacy, digital culture and etiquette competencies, as well as the ability to collaborate effectively in virtual space. The corresponding indicators of the levels are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Levels of Development of Network Communicative Culture and Digital Etiquette Skills

Reproductive Level of NCC and DE		
Component	Role	Functions
Subject Knowledge	Helps teachers confidently and qualitatively transmit educational (subject) information (material), providing students with a basis for developing their functional literacy.	Enriches the content of subject communication, contributes to the formation of critical thinking and deep understanding of the topic (subject, discipline) in students.
Pedagogical Knowledge	Helps teachers consciously understand, integrate, adapt, and apply theoretical, practical, and managerial aspects of constructive teaching and learning	Constructs a holistic pedagogical process, develops respectful and constructive interaction between the teacher and students, forms an educational collaborative atmosphere, and stimulates the teacher's professional development
Technological Knowledge	Helps teachers consciously use new technologies and modern tools in education and student learning.	Allows creation of interactive, multimedia educational environments and implementation of interactive learning platforms and technologies.
Productive Level of NCC and DE		
Component	Role	Functions
Reflection Skills	Helps teachers constructively analyze their own teaching and learning practice, identifying and evaluating its strengths and weaknesses.	Creates an atmosphere of openness and readiness for constructive changes in the educational process, improving teaching and learning quality, and contributing to the teacher's personal and professional development
Critical Thinking Skills	Helps teachers consciously observe, objectively analyze, critically evaluate, and effectively use information in the educational process	Forms in teachers and students the ability for constructive analysis and justification of their own viewpoints based on reliable facts and arguments.
Communication Skills	Helps teachers realize the importance of verbal and non-verbal communication skills necessary for effective interaction with subjects of the pedagogical process (teachers, students)	Creates a safe atmosphere of trust and collaboration necessary for productive educational processes, simplifies communication and joint work, making learning more accessible and engaging.
Digital Communication Skills	Helps teachers consciously apply modern digital communication technologies in the educational process.	Allows creation of networks (chats) of contacts and collaboration, forming cultural and ethical norms of communication in educational online environments
Creative Level of NCC and DE		
Component	Role	Functions
Digital Literacy and Competencies Skills	Helps teachers consciously and optimally effectively use digital resources and platforms	Ensures successful use of digital technologies and tools in the educational process and contributes to reducing digital inequality
Digital Culture and Etiquette Skills	Helps teachers realize the importance of adhering to the code (norms) of behavior in digital educational spaces	Contributes to creating a safe and respectful educational online environment where all communication participants feel comfortable and secure
Collaborative Skills in Virtual Spaces	Helps teachers consciously build effective and safe interpersonal relationships.	Forms a collaborative environment, develops teamwork skills, teaches working and jointly designing educational initiatives in diverse environments, and develops network communicative culture

The matrix makes it possible to conceptualize the formation of network communication culture and digital etiquette as an integrated and systemic developmental model aimed at enhancing teachers' professional competence and students' digital responsibility.

Conclusions

It should be emphasized that the development of digital competencies—from communication ethics and culture to forming reflective and critical thinking—is one of the key tasks of modern higher education. To enhance the level of NCC and DE development, massive open online courses (MOOCs) have been developed, targeted at faculty and students of higher education institutions.

Forming network communicative culture and digital etiquette for teachers and students in "online communities" is not just "culture" and "etiquette," but a synthesis of concepts such as "safety," "collaboration," "critical thinking," "cooperation," "customization," as well as high professional mastery of the teacher in effective teaching and learning in digital spaces. Thus, customization of the system for forming network communicative culture and digital etiquette in universities is a key factor for successfully integrating online platforms into the educational process, creating a comfortable and productive educational environment for students' successful adaptation to new educational technologies, communication, and rules of ethical behavior, including in network communities.

Thus, the customization and institutionalization of the system for forming network communicative culture and digital etiquette in universities serve as a strategic condition for the successful integration of online plat-

forms into the educational process. This, in turn, ensures the creation of a comfortable, technologically advanced, and productive educational environment, while also promoting students' effective adaptation to modern digital technologies, communication formats, and norms of ethical behavior, including rules of network interaction in professional and academic digital communities.

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